

ASSESSMENT OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF DUMP TRUCKS IN OPEN MINES

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***Аннотация:** Статья посвящена оценке энергоэффективности самосвалов, используемых на открытых карьерах. Энергоэффективность является критически важным аспектом в горнодобывающей промышленности, так как напрямую влияет на производительность, эксплуатационные расходы и экологические показатели. В статье представлены методы оценки расхода топлива, анализа эксплуатационных характеристик и оптимизации маршрутов самосвалов. Также рассматриваются современные технологии, способствующие повышению энергоэффективности, такие как системы управления, мониторинга и автоматизации. Основные результаты исследования включают выявление факторов, влияющих на энергозатраты, и рекомендации по улучшению эксплуатационных характеристик самосвалов. Статья предназначена для специалистов горнодобывающей промышленности, инженеров и руководителей, занимающихся эксплуатацией оборудования.*

***Ключевые слова:** энергоэффективность, самосвалы, открытые карьеры, горнодобывающая промышленность, расход топлива, оптимизация маршрутов, современные технологии, автоматизация, экологические показатели, эксплуатационные характеристики.*

***Annotation:** The article is devoted to the assessment of energy efficiency of dump trucks used in open pit mines. Energy efficiency is a critical aspect in the mining industry, as it directly affects productivity, operating costs and environmental performance. The article presents methods for assessing fuel*

consumption, analyzing operating characteristics and optimizing dump truck routes. It also discusses modern technologies that contribute to improving energy efficiency, such as control, monitoring and automation systems. The main results of the study include identifying factors affecting energy costs and recommendations for improving the operational characteristics of dump trucks. The article is intended for mining industry specialists, engineers and managers involved in equipment operation.

Keywords: *energy efficiency, dump trucks, open pit mines, mining industry, fuel consumption, route optimization, modern technologies, automation, environmental indicators, operational characteristics.*

Energy Consumption Analysis

The energy consumption of MHT is affected by various parameters, with equipment characteristics and operating conditions being the most significant factors. These parameters play a crucial role in determining the overall energy usage of MHT during its operations. This research applied a consistent base truck configuration and utilized the same haul road profile, which is part of the operating conditions. Additionally, an important aspect of the operating conditions is the force parameters that the trucks experience on the road. These force parameters have a significant impact on the energy consumption of the trucks (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Force parameters of MHT [27].

They are (Figure 1):

- (a) Rolling Resistance (RR), which is the force that resists motion when the truck tyre rolls on the haul road.
- (b) GVW, which represents the total weight of MHT. It equals the weight of the empty vehicle plus the rated payload.
- (c) Rimpull Force (RF), which offers rimpull power to change the speed of a truck. It is sourced from the on-board engine.
- (d) Drag Force (DF), which means aerodynamic resistance, It is the force that resists air drag when the truck operates.
- (e) Braking Force (BF), which is the force that reduces truck speed, especially on the downhill section.

According to Newtonian mechanics, when MHT is cruising at constant speed on flat roads ($\varphi = 0$), the mechanical power consumed is spent to overcome the RR with the ground and the DF of the truck. The kinetic force is modelled as follows:

$$F_R = C_R mg \quad (1)$$

$$F_D = \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho A V^2 \quad (2)$$

$$F_{RI} = m \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (3)$$

$$F_K = C_R mg + \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho A V^2 + m \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (4)$$

where F_R is rolling resistance force; F_D is drag force; F_{RI} is rimpull force; F_K is kinetic force; C_R and C_D are the RR and DF coefficients, respectively; ρ is the air density, kg/m^3 ; and A is the cross-sectional area of the vehicle, m^2 ; g is the gravitational acceleration, kg/s^2 ; m is the GVW, kg ; v is instant speed, m/s .

When MHT is operating on an uphill section ($\varphi \neq 0$), the mechanical power consumed is spent to overcome the RR with the ground, the DF, the grade component of the GVW, and the acceleration of the truck. The kinetic force is modelled as follows:

$$F_K = C_R mg \cos \varphi + \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho A V^2 + mg \sin \varphi + m \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (5)$$

when MHT is operating on a downhill section ($\varphi \neq 0$), the mechanical power consumed is spent to overcome the RR with the ground, the DF, the grade component of the GVW, and the acceleration of the truck. The braking force is modelled as follows:

$$F_B = -C_R mg \cos \varphi - \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho A V^2 + mg \sin \varphi + m \frac{dV}{dt} \quad (6)$$

where F_B is braking force; φ is the angle of ramp road.

Energy Consumption Calculation

All parts of energy consumption are modelled as following:

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 W_R = \int C_R mg(\cos\varphi) ds \\
 W_D = \int \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho AV^2 ds \\
 W_{RI} = \int m \frac{dV}{dt} ds \\
 W_G = \int mg(\sin\varphi) ds \\
 W_B = \int -C_R mg \cos\varphi - \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho AV^2 + mg \sin\varphi + m \frac{dV}{dt} ds \\
 W_{ER} = \frac{1}{2} W_B \\
 W_{TW} = W_R + W_D + W_{RI} + W_G + W_B - W_{ER} \\
 \left\{ \begin{array}{l}
 W_{ACE} = C_{ACE} W_{TW} \\
 W_{CE} = C_{CE} W_{TW} \\
 W_{HE} = C_{HE} W_{TW} \\
 W_{AE} = W_{ACE} + W_{CE} + W_{HE} \\
 W_{OTW} = W_{TW} + W_{AE}
 \end{array} \right.
 \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

where W_R , W_D , W_{RI} , W_G , W_B are rolling resistance energy, drag energy, rimpull energy, gravitational potential energy, and braking energy in kWh, respectively. It is the default configuration for battery alternatives to install an ERS, which can capture approximately 50% of braking energy for the on-board battery for further use [8]. W_{TW} represents the total work source from all force parameters, kWh. Apart from the force energy, there is also consideration for the auxiliary energy required to power other onboard components. This auxiliary energy, although relatively small compared to the kinetic energy required, accounts for approximately 10–20% of the total force energy. The specific percentage may vary depending on the specific powertrain configurations implemented in the MHT. In Equation (7), W_{AE} means the total energy of the auxiliary system. Which consists of air conditioner energy (W_{ACE}), cooling energy (W_{CE}), and hydraulic energy (W_{HE}), kWh. C_{ACE} means the coefficient of air conditioning, which is 1–3% for diesel alternatives, and the mean is 2%, while it is 0% for battery alternatives due to no operator. C_{CE} is the coefficient of cooling system, which is 5–7% for diesel alternatives, and the mean is 6%, while it is 8–12% for battery alternatives, and the mean is 10% because battery packages have a higher cooling requirement for maintaining normal performance. C_{HE} is the coefficient of the hydraulic system, which is 2% for diesel and battery alternatives. W_{OTW} represents the overall total energy of force energy and auxiliary energy that the truck needs in the whole haul cycle. The energy consumption of each part for 5 applications is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Energy consumption (kWh) heatmap.

The energy requirements per cycle for different applications vary significantly. Figure 8 provides an energy comparison of all alternatives in terms of rimpull energy, drag energy, rolling resistance energy, and gravitational potential energy. TAT requires the highest total work of rimpull (TWRI), while BOT consumes the least. Despite the low speed on the haul road, the total work of drag (TWD) still shows that BT-S consumes more energy compared to others due to its faster speed. The total work of rolling resistance (TWR) and the total work of gravity (TWG) are the two major components of energy consumption. DET and BOT consume higher rolling resistance energy due to the 2.5% rolling resistance coefficient on the haul ramp, which is higher than the 1.5% coefficient on the trolley ramp. However, it should be noted that these calculations assume that all alternatives

have the same GVW, which is why the gravitational potential energy is the same for all trucks. In reality, due to differences in onboard battery size and powertrain specifications, the gravitational potential energy required for each truck alternative would likely slightly differ.

Due to the GVW and significant changes in operating elevation, MHT experiences substantial loss of potential energy as it descends haul ramps in surface mines. To mitigate this energy loss, ERS technology is successfully employed in various industrial applications to recover potential energy and reduce the amount of energy required to be carried onboard. In Figure 4, it is evident that braking energy constitutes a relatively small portion of the total energy consumption. In this study, it is assumed that half of the braking energy is captured through the implementation of ERS.

Figure 3. Energy consumption comparison of rimpull, drag, rolling resistance, and gravity.

Figure 4. Energy consumption comparison of braking.

The primary contributors to energy consumption, including total work of force (W_{TWF}) and auxiliary energy (W_{AE}), are the on-board energy sources such as the diesel tank and battery packages. Figure 10a illustrates the components of on-board energy consumption, including diesel energy (W_{DE}) and battery energy (W_{BE}). Trolley power proves effective in reducing the amount of on-board energy that needs to be carried. Although hydraulic energy (W_{HE}), air conditioner energy (W_{ACE}), and cooling energy (W_{CE}) constitute small portions of the total energy consumption, they still consume a significant amount of on-board energy, particularly W_{CE} in battery applications. In Figure 5b, the overall total energy (W_{OTW}) consumption for each

application is presented. The results indicate that manual diesel-electric trucks have the highest energy consumption (681 kW/h), while automatic battery trolley dynamic trucks have the lowest energy consumption (626 kW/h). According to this study, the total energy gap between the different alternatives is less than 7%. However, if the study considers a higher proportion of trolley ramps and incorporates the impact of battery size and engine specifications, the gap between diesel trucks and battery alternatives may widen.

Figure 5. Energy consumption comparison of W_{DE}/W_{BE} and W_{OTW} .

Conclusions

This paper has introduced battery MHT applications in mine sites, including truck performance associated with hypothetical road simulation, energy consumption based on force parameters, and battery size design according to current battery technology, which is used as a technical estimation to widely deploy battery alternatives. Conclusions are as follows:

- (1) Due to the TAT, BT-D, and BT-S configuration requirements, the haul road design should add a trolley ramp with a flat road for the accelerating truck to arrive at required the approach speed. The performance of each application is quite different: BT-S has the fastest speed (27 km/h) on the trolley ramp, while DET is

the slowest (12 km/h) of the five applications. However, from the cycle time perspective, BOT needs the longest cycle time (2500 s), while its BT-D counterpart is only 1817 s due to the battery swapping operation for BOT.

(2) Rolling resistance energy and gravitational potential energy are the biggest components in MHT energy consumption. Because the trolley application and ERS can effectively save energy for MHT alternatives, the total energy consumption of all applications is: DET—681 kWh; TAT—673 kWh; BOT—645 kWh; BT-S—637 kWh; BT-D—626 kWh. The on-board diesel or battery energy (excluding trolley power) required by these alternatives is DET—681 kWh; BOT—645 kWh; TAT—511 kWh; BT-S—471 kWh; BT-D—466 kWh, of which BT-D shows the best energy consumption performance.

(3) This study selected LFP and LTO as battery sizing chemical materials due to their relatively higher cycle times, significantly longer life-spans, high energy density, and reliability in terms of efficiency, power, and safety. In regard to battery utilisation, battery package design shows only 35% of the battery “nameplate” capacity is real effective utilisation due to discharging range loss (25%), battery degradation loss (20%), and battery efficiency loss (20%). Based on tailored battery size selection, BOT, BT-D and BT-S need 25 tonnes, 18 tonnes and 18 tonnes LFP battery mass while they need 50 tonnes, 36 tonnes and 36 tonnes LTO battery mass respectively. After two haul cycles, the SOC of BOT, BT-D and BT-S is 1949 kWh, 2284 kWh and 1386 kWh, respectively. Based on unified battery size selection, BOT, BT-D, and BT-S need 25 t LFP battery mass, while they need 50 t LTO battery mass, respectively. After two haul cycles, the SOC of BOT, BT-D, and BT-S is 1949 kWh, 3282 kWh, and 2384 kWh. The resulting NPV of costs for different applications over 20 years is USD

3.7 M, USD 4.6 M, USD 4.6 M, USD 3.6 M, USD 4.4 M, and USD 4.4 M for LFP/BT-S, LFP/BT-D, LFP/BOT, LTO/BT-S, LTO/BT-D, and LTO/BOT, respectively. BT-S shows a significant advantage in on-board battery cost, taking

into consideration an over hundred truck fleet in a big surface mine. The cost savings will be increased when the battery exchange expenditure is accounted.

A comprehensive techno-economic assessment was conducted to identify a feasible battery size in this study. In future research, it is recommended to develop a more accurate battery size model that considers additional factors specific to the unique conditions of mine sites. For instance, this study assumed favourable weather conditions with a constant temperature and typical long-distance haul roads in the battery sizing model. To further enhance research, utilizing real-world data to investigate actual route lengths and generate corresponding distributions would be beneficial. The decarbonisation of trucks should be evaluated on a case-by-case basis, as the risks and benefits will vary among different mines. With the industry's growth and increasing decarbonisation efforts, advancements in renewable generation, battery technology, and alternative vehicles will make the business case for decarbonisation more compelling.

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